

Element Elevators? - Tracing element transport in shear zones at Cap de Creus, Spain

Dörte Jordan^{1,2,*}, Klaus Wemmer³, Mathias Hueck⁴, Leo Kriegsman^{1,2}

¹ Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Dept. of Research & Education, Leiden, Netherlands

² Utrecht University, Faculty of Geosciences, Dept. of Earth Sciences, Netherlands

³ Geowissenschaftliches Zentrum Göttingen, Georg-August Universität Göttingen, Germany

⁴ Ruhr-Universität Bochum, Germany

* doerte.jordan@naturalis.nl

Fluid-rock interaction is a key factor in resource formation. Next to leaching, dissolution, and precipitation, metamorphic reactions are main factors to release ligands and ions into solution. Combining petrography, element maps, and whole rock analysis allows us to trace element transport. Thereby, we want to constrain how element transfer in shear zones is linked to the crustal water cycle.

Shear zones are ideal tectonic settings to study element transport in the Earth's crust as they can sample the brittle-ductile transition. Furthermore, along the peninsula of Cap de Creus, Spain, fault gouges, pseudotachylites, and mylonites are in proximity, affecting the same units.

At Cap de Creus, we sampled a total of five sets of shear zones. This means, proto-mylonite, mylonite, and ultra-mylonite covering the highly deformed area of the Natural Park. To gain further insight into the influence of different lithologies, sample sets of meta-sediments, pegmatite, paragneiss, and plagio-amphibolite were taken. Additionally, reference material from less deformed meta-sediments, plagio-amphibolite, and pegmatite was sampled for comparison.

Petrography shows a change in the modal mineral composition. Moving from the proto-mylonite to the ultra-mylonite, the composition shifts towards quartz enrichment. The pegmatite, however, can preserve some of the tourmaline, which is then strongly thinned out and elongated. Element maps and chemical analysis will be the underlying data to discuss element transfer on a meter scale in this specific tectonic setting. We expect relatively high geochemical changes the closer we get to the ultra-mylonite.

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